

Supplementary Figure S1. Ethanol stress induced ER autophagy. Electron micrographs of BY4741 treated with 8% ethanol for 6 h. Vacuolar membrane invagination and the immersion of the ER in can be seen (A-B and E). The double membrane structures that belong to the ER are observed inside the vacuole (C-D) and also in the cellular cortex as ER whorls (F). Vacuole is indicated (V).

